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Corruption Assessment and Underdevelopment of Nigeria Educational System (2015-2023)

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Abstract

Despite significant investments in education, the Nigerian educational sector continues to nosedive and grapple with debilitating challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, declining academic standards, poor funding and supervisory capacity by school-based management boards. Corruption is not just widespread but it is systemic and responsible largely for the country's underdevelopment. The research critically examines the nexus between corruption and underdevelopment of Nigeria's educational system from 2015 to 2023. The objective to this research is to investigate manifestation of corruption in the educational system in Nigeria, including embezzlement, nepotism, and bribery, and its impact on the sector's performance. To guide this research, questions were formulated, and principal/agent theory was used as theoretical framework, while the study employed contents analysis through the use of qualitative secondary data. Some of the research findings responsible for corruption and underdevelopment of Nigerian educational systems includes low level of transparency and accountability, inflation of contract and kickbacks, poor remuneration leading to misappropriation or diversion of educational fund, over invoicing and false declaration, theft of intellectual property, piracy and plagiarism. The research concluded that Nigerian government

should discourage excessive materialism and culture of “get rich quick” in Nigerian society; and properties of such persons proven to have accrued wealth dubiously should be forfeited to their government. The study recommends that a branch of anti-corruption boards should be established in all educational institutions and made functional so that cases of corruptions can be detected early enough and reported for prosecution.

Keywords: Corrupt Practices, Bribery, Siphoning, Educational System, Nigerian Government, Underdevelopment, Dependency

Introduction

Governance is a series of public activities that entails making choices in public interest for the well-being of a nation. Corruption in Nigeria is not just wide spread, but it has become systemic largely a bane in the country's underdevelopment. Nigeria is one of the countries in Africa that loses billions of dollars yearly because of corruption. She was ranked second most corrupt country in the world in 2015 by Transparency International (TI, 2016). In 2016, Nigeria was ranked 17th out of 146 countries by Transparency International Corruption Perception Index (TICPI). By 2019, Nigeria was ranked 32nd most corrupt countries in the world out of 146 countries by TICPI (Unini, 2020). Corruption is a multifaceted phenomenon with multiple causes and effects in Nigeria. It consists of trinity of illegal money, commercial and criminal activities (Mohammed, 2013). In Nigeria, section 8 (1) of the Anti-Corruption Law 2004 stated that corruption is the art of asking for, receiving or obtaining any property or benefit of any kind for oneself or for any other person (Mohammed, 2013). It involves the abuse of public office for self-aggrandizement or private benefits (World Bank, 2014). The term corruption covers a wide range of conduct patterns. It is a product of the socio-economic and political structure of any society. As a multifaceted phenomenon, no single theory is sufficient enough to explain its causation and control. Corruption is an English word. It is not a Nigerian concept. It has western orientations found in other cultures. It is a global problem with certain destructive tendencies in the Third World countries like Nigeria. It is a devilish back up that stare humanity in the world (World Bank, 2014).

The rate of corruption in Nigeria is so alarming that one is constrained to ask the following - is there anything to the nature of Nigerians, or is corruption in Nigeria peculiar; or is corruption in Nigeria generic to

particular certain classes of people? Achebe, (1983) quoting from *Weekly Star* Newspaper of May 15th 1983, wrote that the corrupt nature of the Nigerian society is such that keeping an average Nigerian from being corrupt is like keeping a goat from eating yam. In other words, many are in waiting list to get the privilege. Corruption is often a spring board to underdevelopment of any society and the Nigerian state unfortunately have become a victim of corruption.

In the context of educational system in Nigeria, corruption has eaten deep in the management and administrations of education in Nigeria (Kirya, 2019). For examples, corruption in Nigerian educational system had led to lack of accountability and improper management of resources allocated to public institutions leading to frequent strikes by labour organizations of these institutions in Nigeria. Based on this, the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) have been on loggerhead with subsequent Nigerian governments on poor funding, lack of accountability, imposition of pseudo administrators of public institutions, awarding educational contracts on patronage, and withholding the rights of workers in educational institution which often promotes negative tendencies of self -help and other vices in order to alleviate inadequacies. Most economic, social and political problems in underdeveloped societies like Nigeria usually emanate from corruption manifested in diversion of public resources to private ownership leading to overnight success by public official with impunity, which often propelled others to see corruption as turn by turn in management of public sector (Olukoyede, 2025). In Nigeria case, *emilokan* (it is my [or our] turn) has been popularized and accepted in Nigeria in form of leadership rotation in public sector administration. In the educational sector, there are several types of discrimination. Usually, some are even backed by Nigerian constitution in the name of catchment areas in admission, disadvantaged zones or states, quota system which often sacrifices merit for mediocrity in awarding scholarship admission. All these constitutional methods adopted in Nigeria, including indigene-ship and tribalism have led to square peg in a round hole in admission and employment opportunities in public and private schools leading to quackery, inefficiency and millipede growth in socio-political and economic development.

The problem of corruption in Nigeria is historical. For example, in the colonial administrations, the Northern Nigeria were discriminated in parliamentary seats in Lagos by colonial governors. They were ruled by

proclamation until 1946 Richard Constitution that brought Northern Nigeria to participate in legislation in Lagos. Corruption made the Nigerian founding father to form political parties under tribal linages which brought turn-ship in management of Nigerian state till date. In developed states like America, the idea of spoil system has been ruled out long ago for merit. That was why Barrack Obama an Afro-American was elected based on merit and not race or colour. Nigerian corruption is rooted in political economy of the state with government functionaries displaying public arrogance, exporting ill-gotten wealth abroad, capturing political offices with impunity, and engaging juicy contracts in rotation among their cronies and benefactors. Although, several governments in Nigeria have claimed to be fighting corruption, but unfortunately those who claimed to be waging war against corruption most time become more corrupt than their clients. For example, many billions were claimed to have been recovered from General Abacha and others in the past, but the recovered billions have not been properly re-invested for public use (Yusuf, 2023). Most time, these public officers who were accused of corruption usually muzzled their way to legislative house while others are compensated with ministerial appointment thereby opening wider windows for systemic corruption to persist. This kind of cycle of corruption has continued to perpetuate underdevelopment in Nigeria, most importantly on educational sector which supposed to be the engine room for growth and development. Achebe (1983) squarely maintained that the trouble with Nigeria is simply leadership failures. He maintained that there is nothing wrong with Nigerian land, climate, water or air, but corruption has insulated our leaders not to rise to their responsibilities which is the hallmark of true leadership, The causes of corruption are numerous, some say poverty while others see it as greed. However, whichever way, it has eaten deep characterized by shaky foundations of family moral upbringing at home and in schools. Corruption trends in every structure of Nigeria society hence the need for this conference becomes absolutely inevitable. It is so bad that corruption has been institutionalized to a point where it passes for official policy in both public and private sector of Nigerian national life. The educational system, socio-economic and political system appear to be built on corruption; and even the religions are not immune from corruption in Nigeria society. Therefore, this study attempts to assess the impacts of corruption in

Nigerian educational system with a view of suggesting alternative approach of arresting the phenomenon.

Statement of the Problem

The educational administration system in Nigeria has faced major challenges at all levels of academics. Stakeholders often complains about the rising tide of corruption in Nigeria educational system. It is biting very hard in the academic sector where students ought to have learned ethic and good moral conduct ends up to become fraudsters, drug barons, prostitutes, and kidnapers; to the extent that ritualism or “yahoo” has become the new norms in Nigerian society. These vices are manifested towards personal gains and not political or socio-economic development of Nigeria. Students from corrupt educational system see the Nigerian state as a cash cow to be siphoned for material self -puffery. Nigerian state seems to be helpless hence the leadership themselves are product of corruption because most of the public officers rigged election to disenfranchised public opinion poll despite mass outcry. Nowadays, banditry and kidnapping are booming as a lucrative business with all levels of governments watching with gaze and akimbo for years of these evil practices. The purpose of the study is to assess corruption and underdevelopment of Nigerian educational system with the aim of identifying administrative strategies that can be employed to curb corruption in Nigeria educational system for growth and development.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify forms of corruption and its effects in Nigerian educational system.
2. To identify administrative strategies necessary to curb corruption in educational system of Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What are the forms and effects of corruption in Nigerian educational system?
2. What are the necessary administrative strategies that can be employed in curbing corruption in Nigerian educational system?

Literature Review

Attempt by countries in Africa to break the cycle of underdevelopment has been hindered by the high level of corruption in the continent. Africa is rich in natural resources and the proceeds from the sales of these natural resources to other countries are mismanaged by African leaders through corrupt processes (TI, 2016).

Corruption

TI, (2016) defines corruption as the abuse of power by individuals to whom is entrusted for private benefit. Since the early 1960s when most African countries gained independence, the rich nations of the world have extended development aids to Africa, yet Africa remains the least developed continent in the world. Different schools of thought - modernist and dependency theorists have come out with the causes of underdevelopment in Africa. For instance, the modernist school believes that Africa needs to follow the development part of the industrialized nations before it can develop (Wendt, 1999). On the contrary, the dependency theorists argued that the exploitation of African by the superpowers was responsible for African underdevelopment (Rodney, 2005). However, there is the new school of thought that postulates corruption in Africa hinders development (Amin, 1976). Corruption affects the development in various ways. For example, billions of dollars that would have been used to provide social amenities in some African countries such as Nigeria are siphon and kept in foreign accounts. The former World Bank president, Paul Wolfowitz revealed that public officials in Nigeria have embezzled more than \$300 billion from the nation's pulse for the past forty decades (Ndibe, 2006). Tanzi & Hamid, (2012) detected four outlets through which corruption may have adverse effect on economic growth:

- ✓ Higher public investment,
- ✓ Lower government revenues,
- ✓ Lower expenditure on business operations and maintenance, and
- ✓ Lower quality of public infrastructure.

Education

On education, Orukotan, (2006) quoted UNESCO as an organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills and understanding valuable for all activities of life. In other words,

educational system must strive towards achieving stated and implied objectives perhaps through a lot of complex interactions between individuals and groups. Uneke, (2010) said education is the most powerful instrument for inculcating into citizens of any country good attributes and values for national building. Through education a child attitude and character is sharpened with relevant skills, knowledge and competence needed in economic, social and political development of the society (Uneke, 2010). Orukotan, (2006) noted that education is fundamental human right as everyone has the right to be educated. Education in all ramifications is the main driver of development in areas of human capital, economic and political. National Policy on Education for Nigeria (NPE), (2014) recognized education as a pillar for the piloting of national development in Nigeria. Indeed, any society striving to restructure into international standard must invest largely in education. Secondary education in Nigeria is often to help individuals live a useful life in the society as well as to prepare them for higher education. It is imperative to note that a child that possesses secondary education must be capable of making useful contributions to the development of society (Fafunwa, 1974). No wonder in Nigerian 1999 constitution as amended for example, the minimum requirement for a citizen of Nigeria to become president, governor, or Local government chairperson is O' Level certificate obtained at secondary education level. This is to say that education, at secondary schools must be of good quality in all ramifications. Therefore, good quality secondary education is prelude to prepare the individuals into tertiary education for skillful research needed for national development of the society. Quality education implies that the facilities, infrastructures, information and communication technology, relevant curriculum are procured and teachers of the right quality and quantity at different levels of education are hired to nurture the minds of these students towards goal attainment. Fafunwa, (1974) added that the idea of education makes him refer to curriculum as the whole of the educative process, that is total environment in which education takes place. A major challenge to educational system in Nigeria is corruption (Okogbule & Samuel, 2025). This why the study becomes imperative to peruse leeway of alleviating this long-standing under-development variable of Nigeria state.

Underdevelopment

Underdevelopment makes sense as a means of comparing levels of development. Rodney, (2005) maintained that underdevelopment is often tied to the facts that human social, political and economic development has been uneven because some human groups have advanced further by producing more and becoming wealthier than others. After independence was granted to many African countries, the political leaders of the new independent states began to initiate development policies that will make Africa move away from the underdevelopment stage to a more developed and prosperous continent. Some of the development approaches undertaken by African leaders in the various countries include:

- Import-Substitution Model (IS)
- Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP)

▪ *Import-Substitution Model*

This is an economic and trade policy that discourages the importation of foreign goods and the encouragement of local production for exportation. The challenge of development that was confronting developing countries prior to independence prompted these countries to enact this development policy. This policy has made some of the Latin American countries such as Argentina, Brazil and Mexico to be emerging developing countries of the world. But after most of the colonial masters have left Africa, the continent began to experience lots of social, economic and political challenges. To break away from these challenges, majorities of the emerging Africa states incorporated the Import-Substitution Industrialization Strategy. It must be noted that, in Sub-Sahara Africa, the government took up the leadership of a total undeveloped economies with lack of public finance and without vital institutions to run the government, as well as the lack of human and physical capital (World Bank, 2014). The absence of institutional approach to guide the policy failed to address African developmental challenges because African leaders cornered the opportunity to build their pockets instead of public.

▪ *Structural Adjustment Programmes*

Again, after independence African countries experienced lack of economic growth, standard of living and trade deficit owing to low productivity. Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2009) stated that by the beginning of

the 1980s most of the African countries were in severe economic difficulties with extreme inflation, unfavourable balance of payments and fiscal deficit. FAO, (2009) maintained that in order to solve these economic problems, the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF) and other donor agencies sold the idea of the Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP) to African countries for economic improvement of the continent. The structural adjustment programmes were unable to solve the developmental crisis in Africa because of large scale mass corruption of the political leaders. Instead, the policy led to the mass retrenchment of public office workers and increase poverty in the continent (FAO, 2009).

Theoretical Framework

Principal /Agent Theory

Corruption in Nigeria educational system can be viewed through 'Principal/Agent Theory' developed by (Becker & Stigler, 1974). The theory of principal - agent theory follows from the relationship between an agent and principal. The principal is a task giving person and the agent is the person who receives and executes the task. The agent has to attempt to complete the task, which also involves some sacrifices. Problems can happen when asymmetric information is revealed to the principal and the agent. The sum is that the principal and the agent have distinct objective interests in the beginning (Becker & Stigler, 1974). In this study the principal is embodied as the public interest and the agent as people pursuing corrupt transactions (private pocket). Corruption happens when, for the sake of his or her own self-interest, an agent misleads the principal's interests. This is possible due to crooked information that has emerged between the two elements.

Methodology

The research employs in-depth descriptive qualitative content analysis of corruption in the Nigerian educational system (2015 - 2023). The study perused thoroughly secondary data publications in textbooks, journal articles and online media on issues relating to corruption in Nigeria with special focus to the educational sector. The data for this research was collected through systematic literature reviews (SLR) of the educational sector in Nigerian state.

Results

Corruption and its effects in Nigerian Educational System

Nigeria was ranked 33 most corrupt countries in the world (TI, 2016). Corruption has eaten deep into the fabrics of the Nigerian society and that has been contributing factor responsible for the crisis of development in the country. In the educational sector, the National Policy on Education 2014 was an instrument designed for economic, social and political transformation and national development. The policy made provisions for various levels of basic education - primary 6 years, secondary (3 at junior and 3 at higher college), and tertiary 4 years respectively (NPE, 2014). Nigeria ironically is the sixth largest producer of oil according to (TI, 2016). But corruption in the year 2015 - 2023 both in public and private sectors have led to stagnation in the educational advancement of the economy. For examples there are evidences of shortage of infrastructures in various institutions of learnings in Nigeria; such as classes without roofs, non-availability of desks, and chalkboards characterized by principal / agent theory. Other effects of corruption in Nigerian educational sector (Unini, 2020):

- a. Inadequate professionals or mediocre teachers leading to poor quality of graduates or unemployable scholars in various levels of education in Nigeria.
- b. Lack of instructional materials as a result of crooked agents working for their principals in ministries and government agencies.
- c. Reduction in capacity training of manpower needs of educational sector through training of the trainers as it were in Teachers Training Colleges (TTC)
- d. Corruption have led to frequent and widespread examination malpractices in Nigeria. Parents acting as agents using special centres for their kids and cronies. The outcomes is usually pseudo graduates that has nothing to offer on Nigerian growth and advancement.
- e. Corruption erodes public trust in educational institutions in Nigeria thereby making youths to abandon academic curriculum into yahoo plus, ritual killings and kidnapping in order to boost money making ego.
- f. Corruption have led to undermining teachers' motivation leading to unending strikes among Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in Nigeria, and National Union of Teachers (NUT) from 2015 - 2023.

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- g. Corruption have led to piracy, plagiarism and cutting corners in Nigeria.

Administrative Strategies Necessary to Curb Corruption in Educational System of Nigeria

Nigeria educational system is critical to realization of objective of the global age in line with Vision 2020 and 7 -Point Agenda inaugurated by Federal Government of Nigeria through human capital empowerment for national development. There is general consensus in international community that education has an important role to play in sustainable development in socio-economic, poverty reduction and good governance. In order to achieve these global goals and objectives, the following administrative strategies are needed to curb corruption in Nigerian educational system (TI, 2016):

- a. Strengthening good governance and accountability through transparent practices in allocating and managing educational funds.
- b. Regular auditing of educational institutions by external auditors and forensic assessors.
- c. To put in place anti- crime agencies in various institutions of learning in Nigeria as watchdogs.
- d. Motivation and recognition of teaching profession as a noble career in public and private services.
- e. Promoting transparency in appointment and ethical practices

Discussion

Corruption in the educational system in Nigeria has made some scholars to describe schools as money exchange department to help students pass examinations to become quack 'Doctors', 'Engineers', 'Lawyers' etcetera, instead of institutions of learning to gain admission for higher education and to become specialist in their respective profession. Omotoye, (2009) stated that corruption in political of a nation is a tragedy while corruption in the educational sector is a double tragedy. Corruption in educational sector has tremendous capacity to set in motion an uncontrollable reproductive process in the larger society. This circular tragedy can lead to the following consequences (Omotoye, 2009):

1. **Poor educational administration.** This is to say that recruits into administration of education often times are products of academic cheats, even the administrators of the 'Recruitment Commission' are

most times beneficiaries of money exchange examination malpractices. Merits in promotion of staff into the educational system in Nigeria is usually determined by this circular chain of corrupt officials who often deprive good hands opportunity to contribute to the body of knowledge. The effects are enormous - fake certificate, poor educational administration and poor output in curriculum development.

2. ***Fraudulent educational management.*** Head teachers, Principals of colleges, Rectors, Provost and Vice Chancellors who have invariably benefited from these corrupt chains often transferred developmental funds to their personal bank account for personal use. They are also involved in placing ghost workers on salaries and other manner of over invoicing of contracts.
3. ***Improper assessment of classwork and examination.*** To this regard, students are expected to be evaluated based on the curriculum and set objectives. By and large, corrupt practices frustrate the exercise hence students are exploited in so many ways especially the weak academicals who usually boost to use “what they have and get what they need”. Note, what the weak students usually have are brown envelopes with money or sexual favour to be awarded unqualified marks. Alternatively, these weak students can go extra miles with their parents (product of corrupt chain) to purchase examination question papers before the examination date.

Conclusion

In concluding, all these corrupt practices - lack of meritocracy, fund transfer to private account, gratification, bribery, favoritism and nepotism put together poses obstacle in the educational system in Nigeria. Again, the Nigerian 1999 constitutional policy on ‘quota system’, ‘catchment areas’, or ‘less advantaged areas’ ought not to be extended to educational sector of the economy because it downgrades merits poses obstacle in attainment of qualitative manpower building and national development in era of globalization. Finally, the dialectical consequences of corruption in Nigeria educational system is a bane to all sectorial - economics, social and political underdevelopment.

Recommendations

1. The idea of constitutional policy on quota system, catchment areas or less advantaged states should be abolished to enable merit driven educational sector of the economy. This will go a long way to enhance curriculum objectives.
2. All internal and external examinations should be conducted with the aid of CCTV cameras in order to detect fraudulent examination practices and to sanction or prosecute any defaulters as deterrence to curb malpractices.
3. Parents and guardians should not be seen in the perimeters of any examination hall and students seating arrangement should be four meters apart in both sides of the seating arrangements.
4. Educational sector must be properly funded and equipped both private and public institutions in order to compete favorably with developed countries. This will help to curb brain drain syndrome in the educational sector. In addition, teachers in all levels of academics should be properly remunerated to curb alternative option of meeting up their family and personal needs.

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